

Transport Phenomena in Single Crystal Silicon Plates under Diffusing Manganese

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Abstract: The purpose of this research is to quantify the transport of manganese (Mn) in single crystal silicon [111]. The diffusion coefficient of Mn in Si is determined based upon the data from Secondary Ion Mass Spectroscopy (SIMS) analysis. The silicon samples in form of plates were processed for 1.5 hours at 1000 °C; a layer of Mn powder (99.9% pure) was used as impurity forced by temperature and concentration gradients to be incorporated into the silicon crystal. The estimated value of the diffusion coefficient is $2.71 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The electric property of Si was measured at room temperature, before and after diffusion process. At room temperature the electric conductivity depends on the flux of current and on the magnitude of the electric field. Raman Spectroscopy analysis on the surface of the silicon samples, before and after the diffusion process, shows that the sp³ bonding on the plates was not altered.

Key words: Conductivity, Diffusion Coefficient, Fick's Equation, Transport Phenomena

1 Introduction

In silicon technology is common to produce intrinsic and extrinsic semiconductors. Intrinsic semiconductor is pure silicon, and extrinsic silicon could be p-type or n-type semiconductors. Extrinsic semiconductor is produced by ion implanting and solid state diffusion of non-silicon atoms into the crystal structure of Si. The impurities are atoms of boron, arsenic, phosphorous among others. Little information about Mn ion implanting or thermal diffused is available (Khait, Y. L., et al. 1994). As part of a big picture this job proposes to change the electrical and thermal properties of silicon after doping the substrate with manganese. The resultant material can find applications in thermoelectricity under the effect of reduction in the thermal conductivity, this effect has consistent answer when silicon forms intermetallic compound with strontium and manganese oxide (Seo J.W., Kim C.M., Park K., 2015). The presence of manganese in silicon can be used as a magnetic switch, since manganese shows to have paramagnetic response (Schinzel, S., 2008). Similar jobs are being performed in silicon based materials (Leon, J., et al. 2011), (Lide, D., R., et al. 1996). The manganese into silicon can play a big role related to applications in data processing where the processor can use magnetic fields instead of electrical field. In addition, manganese is chemically inert at room temperature and no oxidation of this element is expected to occur when it diffuses into internal voids of crystalline silicon. Silicon doped with Mn can also withstand under high temperature greater than 1000 degrees (°C), demonstrated by our experiments during 1.5 hours. Manganese could be detrimental for silicon because it can reduce the thermal diffusivity. The thermal diffusivity of Mn is $2.24 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and for Si is $7.6 \times 10^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Callister, W., D, et al. 2007) this effect will be evaluated in a future paper confirming this approach. All these effects of transport phenomena are being evaluated on the surface of the silicon plates.

2 Diffusion Models

2.1 Laplace transform for Gaussian distribution method

Manganese has an ionic radius of 0.067 nm, it all and silicon 0.04 nm. The crystal structure of single crystal Si is cubic diamond and for Mn it is cubic (Callister, W., D, et al. 2007). Mn can be incorporated in silicon because they have similar structure and similar ionic radius. The modeling of diffusion include as basis mass conservation as a general physical constraint that may be imposed on diffusing systems. We assume that the system for which diffusion is occurring neither undergoes radioactive processes nor provides internal active sources for diffusing species. As such, mass is conserved at all points in the medium, even under action of diffusing flux. In cases where species is produced or destroyed from a source, a source term must be added to account for mass conservation. Choose a general point P(x,y,z) in rectangular coordinates fixed to the material, and place around it a small cubical control volume of size $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z$.

Consider the flux J (P) to vary continuously about the point P so that each component is also a continuous function of its coordinates. If the sums of the fluxes entering or leaving opposite faces of the control volume do not balance, a net accumulation occurs. Glicksman (Glicksman, M., E., 2000) has discussed, thus the mass balance may be expressed as:

$$\text{Flow}_{in} - \text{Flow}_{out} = \text{Accumulation Rate} \tag{1}$$

Taking into consideration (1), apply Fick's second law to obtain a second order linear equation that can be related to the linear diffusion. For the following equation the diffusion coefficient (D) is constant.

$$D \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \right) - \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = 0 \tag{2}$$

To solve (2), needs to define the boundary condition of our system. For a one dimensional diffusion, is important to establish that the initial concentration (C_0) of Mn will be maximum at position $x = 0$ and time $t = 0$. Then we say that the concentration (C) of our system can be considered as a function of time and position. The next step is reducing (2) and eliminates the dependence of time using Laplace transform. To obtain a function independent of time (image function- $\bar{C}(x)$) have to use a transform field, but eventually would have to change image function to the desired concentration field (object function- $\bar{C}(x,t)$). Then multiply all (2) by transform parameter or Laplace kernel (e^{-pt}), to obtain the follows equation:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \cdot e^{-pt} dt - \frac{1}{D} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \cdot e^{-pt} dt = 0 \tag{3}$$

To keep developing (3), define the Laplace transform of the concentration field:

$$\bar{C} \equiv \int_0^{\infty} C(x,t) \cdot e^{-pt} dt \tag{4}$$

Substitutes (4) into (3)

$$\frac{d^2 \bar{C}}{dx^2} - \frac{1}{D} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \cdot e^{-pt} dt = 0 \tag{5} \quad \text{Or} \quad \frac{d^2 \bar{C}}{dx^2} = \frac{1}{D} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \cdot e^{-pt} dt \tag{6}$$

To solve the right side of (6) needs to be evaluated by using partial integration:

$$\int_b^a u \cdot v' = uv - \int_b^a v \cdot du \tag{7}$$

Where $u = e^{-pt}$, $dv = \partial C / \partial t dt$, $du = -p e^{-pt}$ and $v = C$, substitutes all this terms into (7) it is obtained:

$$\int_b^a u \cdot dv = (e^{-pt} C) \Big|_0^\infty - \int_0^\infty C - p \cdot e^{-pt} dt \quad (8)$$

Continue reducing the right hand side expression until identify the concentration field (\bar{C}), then, evaluate the initial condition at $t=0$, to obtain the value for C .

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \cdot e^{-pt} dt = -C \Big|_{t=0} + p \int_0^\infty C \cdot e^{-pt} dt \quad (9) \quad \text{Or} \quad \int_0^\infty \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \cdot e^{-pt} dt = -C \Big|_{t=0} + p \bar{C} \quad (10)$$

After being evaluated the right hand side of (10), it's obtained $C = 0$. Then, if combine (10) and (5) into (2) using Laplace transform of Fick's second law the expression will be reduced to:

$$\left(\frac{d^2 \bar{C}}{dx^2} \right) - \frac{p}{D} \cdot \bar{C} = 0 \quad (11)$$

Considering M as a quantity of diffusion at $x=0$ and $t=0$, and that the process of diffusion will be subject to the mass constraint:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} C(x,t) dx = M \quad (12)$$

Applying the Laplace transformed Fick's second law it is obtained:

$$\frac{p}{D} \cdot \bar{C}(x,p) - \frac{d^2 \bar{C}(x,p)}{dx^2} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The partial solution for (13) is:

$$\bar{C} = A \cdot e^{\left(\sqrt{\frac{p}{D}}\right)x} + B \cdot e^{-\left(\sqrt{\frac{p}{D}}\right)x} \quad (14)$$

But the medium of diffusion occurs when $x > 0$, that means the positive root of (14) must be eliminated.

The expression of image function- $(\bar{C}(x,t))$. is:

$$\bar{C} = B \cdot e^{-\left(\sqrt{\frac{p}{D}}\right)x} \quad (15)$$

Taking in consideration the equation (12) for the half space when $x > 0$:

$$\int_0^\infty C(x,t) dx = \frac{M}{2} \quad (16)$$

Then, when apply the Laplace transform to (16) it is obtained:

$$L \left[\int_0^\infty C(x,t) dx \right] = L \left[\frac{M}{2} \right] \quad (17)$$

After calculating the Laplace transform of (17), it is obtained:

$$\int_0^\infty \bar{C}(x,p) dx = \frac{M}{2p} \quad (18)$$

Substitutes (15) into (18):

$$\int_0^{\infty} B \cdot e^{-\left(\sqrt{\frac{p}{D}}\right)x} dx = \frac{M}{2p} \quad (19)$$

Solving for the unknown variable B:

$$B = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{pD}} \quad (20)$$

Substituting (20) into (15), it is obtained:

$$\bar{C}(x, p) = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{pD}} \cdot e^{-\left(\sqrt{\frac{p}{D}}\right)x} \quad (21) \quad \text{Or} \quad \bar{C}(x, p) = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{D}} \cdot \frac{e^{-\left(\sqrt{\frac{p}{D}}\right)x}}{\sqrt{p}} \quad (22)$$

The rearranging of the terms must be performed previously in order to obtain the inverse of Laplace transform of (22):

$$a = x/D^{-1/2} \quad (23)$$

$$L^{-1}(\bar{C}) = C(x, t) = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{D}} L^{-1}\left(e^{-a(\sqrt{p})} p^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}\right) \quad (24)$$

Applying the inverse of Laplace transform through the tables:

$$L^{-1}\left(\frac{e^{-a(\sqrt{p})}}{\sqrt{p}}\right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{a^2}{4t}\right)} \quad (25)$$

To find the concentration field (C (x, t)) in time domain, substituting result of the (25) into (24) shows that:

$$C(x, t) = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{D}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{a^2}{4t}\right)} \quad (26)$$

To determine the diffusion using a Gaussian distribution needs to substitute (23) to

$$\text{obtain: } C(x, t) = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{\pi Dt}} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{x^2}{4Dt}\right)} \quad (27)$$

2.2 Fourier's method

There is another way to determine the diffusion coefficient is through a Fourier's method assuming that the concentration field can be expressed in the form of the product of a periodic function, X(x) and a time-dependent function T(t).

$$C(x, t) = X(x) \cdot T(t) \quad (28)$$

In the case of linear flow, Fick's second law is:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \right) \quad (29)$$

Substituting the product function solution (28) into the left-hand side of (29) yields

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = X(x) \frac{dT(t)}{dt} \quad (30)$$

And similarly, substituting into right-hand side of (29) yields

$$D \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \right) = DT(t) \frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} \quad (31)$$

Equating the right-hand sides of (30) and (31) gives

$$X(x) \frac{dT(t)}{dt} = DT(t) \frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} \quad (32)$$

The variables in (32) may now be separated as:

$$[DT(t)]^{-1} \frac{dT(t)}{dt} = [X(x)]^{-1} \frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} \quad (33)$$

Clearly, the left side of (33) is function of time and the right side of (33) is equal to a function of the distance variable. It follows that both functions must be equal to the same constant. For convenience, this constant is chosen as $-\lambda^2$. The use of periodic eigenfunctions permits the reduction of Fick's second law from a partial equation in x and t , to two ordinary differential equations (ODE): The first is a first order ODE in time, and linear in the temporal function $T(t)$.

$$\frac{dT(t)}{dt} = -D\lambda^2 T(t) \quad (34)$$

The other is a second order ODE in x and linear in the spatial function $X(x)$.

$$\frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} = -D\lambda^2 X(x) \quad (35)$$

Solution of these linear ODE's are well known:

$$\frac{T(t)}{T(0)} = \exp(-D\lambda^2 t) \quad (36) \quad \text{And} \quad X(x) = A \sin(\lambda x) + B \cos(\lambda x) \quad (37)$$

The assumed product function solution, (28), may be found by multiplying together (36) and (37), so the desired periodic concentration solution is:

$$C(x,t) = [AT(0) \sin(\lambda x) + B \cos(\lambda x)] \exp(-\lambda^2 D t) \quad (38)$$

Finally for applications of Fourier's series the following equation must be used:

$$C(x,t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[[A_n \sin(\lambda_n x) + B_n \cos(\lambda_n x)] \exp(-\lambda_n^2 D t) + E \right] \quad (39)$$

Then, (39) must be rearranged in non-dimensionalized by choosing $C(x,t)/C_o$, so rewriting (39) gives the dimensionless solution:

$$\frac{C(x,t)}{C_o} = \frac{h}{l} + \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} \sin\left(n\pi \frac{h}{l}\right) \cos\left(n\pi \frac{x}{l}\right) \exp\left[-\left(\frac{n\pi}{2}\right)^2 \left(\frac{2\sqrt{Dt}}{l}\right)^2\right] \quad (40)$$

This equation is nonlinear respect to the diffusivity (D) and the solution can be determined by numerical method. For the general case for N_L system of nonlinear equations, the matrix notation is: $\mathbf{N}_L = f(x, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{p})$; where x is the independent variable; \mathbf{N} is the vector of the dependent variables; \mathbf{p} is the vector of parameters. The set of equations is solved by estimating the vector \mathbf{p} and the equations can be expressed as $\mathbf{N} = f(x, \mathbf{p})$. For one dependent variable, the sum of squared residuals (\mathbf{R}_s) can be formulated by:

$$\mathbf{R}_s = (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N})^T (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N}) \quad (41)$$

\mathbf{N}_i reports the experimental measurements \mathbf{N} is the vector of the estimate value. For multiple regression including n dependent variables, the weighted sum of squared residuals is:

$$\mathbf{W} = \sum_{k=1}^n w_k \mathbf{s}_k^T \mathbf{s}_k = \sum_{k=1}^n w_k \mathbf{R}_s \quad (42) \quad \text{And} \quad \mathbf{W} = \sum_{k=1}^n w_k (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N})^T (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N}) \quad (43)$$

Where w_k is the weighting factor corresponding to the k th dependent variable; \mathbf{R}_s is the sum of squared residuals corresponding to the k th dependent variable. The Tylor series truncated after the second term converts the nonlinear equation into a linear one:

$$\mathbf{N}(x, \mathbf{p} + \Delta \mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{N}(x, \mathbf{p}) + \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \Delta \mathbf{p} \quad (44)$$

The (44) is linear in $\Delta \mathbf{p}$; The problem is reduced to find the correction of \mathbf{p} in terms of $\Delta \mathbf{p}$, that has to be added to an estimate of \mathbf{p} to minimize the sum of squared residuals. To do this we replaced the estimated values \mathbf{N} by (44) into (43) getting an explicit relationship:

$$\mathbf{W} = (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N} - \mathbf{A} \Delta \mathbf{p})^T (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N} - \mathbf{A} \Delta \mathbf{p}) \quad (45)$$

Where \mathbf{A} is the Jacobian matrix of the partial derivatives of \mathbf{N} with respect to \mathbf{p} , evaluated at all n points where the experimental measurements are available and in matrix notation is:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial p_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial p_k} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{\partial N_n}{\partial p_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial N_n}{\partial p_k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (46)$$

In (45) taking the partial derivative of \mathbf{W} with respect to $\Delta \mathbf{p}$ and equaling to zero, it can be solved $\Delta \mathbf{p}$ which is the correction vector and is given by:

$$\Delta \mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^T (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N}) \quad (47)$$

The new estimated value of \mathbf{p} is:

$$\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}_{\text{previous}} + \Delta \mathbf{p} \quad (48)$$

To solve for the diffusion coefficient, the matrix \mathbf{A} has just one element that is $= \partial N_1 / \partial p_1$, and the other components are all zero (Constantinides A., 1987). Computer programs can be used in advanced to get accuracy results of \mathbf{p} . Our final estimate of \mathbf{p} converges for a value of the diffusion coefficient equal to $2.71 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

3. Experiments conducted

3.1 Procedure

The silicon plates measuring 20 mm wide, 40 mm length and 400 microns thick were processed at 1000 °C into a vacuum chamber for 1.5 hours. Two film plates were supporting powder manganese so that manganese and the silicon plates are like a sandwich. The basic components of the apparatus are: the power source for heating (potentiometer) aimed to increase the temperature inside the closed reactor; a pump to create vacuum pressure inside the reactor; hydrogen was circulating during the time of experiment. Ceramic tubes were used as electrical insulator for the heating element constructed with tungsten wire. The

heating element was assembled into a graphite block to make the heating transfer efficient. The tungsten coil was made by using nine feet wire with 0.635 mm (0.025 inch) in diameter. A thermocouple type K was monitoring the temperature along the experiment. The diffusion of manganese into silicon was driven by the difference in concentration, a pure diffusional process.

Figure 1: Basic components and equipment inside the reactor

The vacuum level was in the order of 10^{-3} torr, the presence of hydrogen inside the chamber prevents the possible entrance of oxygen into the chamber. Figure-1 shows the schematic arrangement of the internal assembly of the vacuum device. After 1.5 hours of processing, the samples were cleaned to remove the excess of manganese by submerging the plates into a liquid solution of a mixture of hydrochloric acid (HCl) and nitric acid (HNO_3). Finally, the samples were washed in distilled water before to proceed with the material characterization analysis.

4. Discussions

The final characterization of the samples includes the Raman Spectroscopy. An argon laser with wavelength of 514.53 nm and 7 mW was induced on the surface of silicon; the zoom resolution of 80X in the sample was recorded. In the graph 2 was observed that the bonding SP³ remained present throughout the diffusion process into the silicon wafers samples. This confirmed that the silicon structure was not altered during the processing of silicon wafers with pure manganese.

Figure 2: Raman Spectroscopy for silicon wafers

The electrical characterization was evaluated to determine the conductivity on the surface of silicon. Figure 3 shows the results before and after diffusing Mn into Si plates in terms of conductivity vs current. An original sample of Si was provided to perform an electrical characterization without being exposed to the experiment. The bottom plate sample, which was one of the plates exposed to extreme conditions such as low vacuum pressure and high temperature during all the experiment was provided to perform an electrical characterization. After analyze the results obtained from the characterization, it can say that the conductivity of the bottom plate was higher than the original Si plate. The two samples processed simultaneously into the vacuum pressure device shows a different conductivity. In addition, the conductivity for the original plate increases more than the Si plate located on top of the sandwich.

Figure 3: Conductivity Comparison before and after

Finally the samples were sent to characterize the presence of Mn using Secondary Ion Mass Spectroscopy, SIMS. This technique can determine the elemental, molecular or isotropic composition as a function of depth (Benninghoven, A., 1994)The data of concentration of Mn as a function of depth into silicon was used to estimate the diffusion coefficient using mathematical approaches. Figure 4 shows the amount of manganese concentration reached in Si plates at different depths in terms of microns.

Figure 4 SIMS Analysis for manganese into silicon plates

The heavy diffusion of Mn into silicon reached a depth of about 10 microns. The diffusion coefficient was evaluated using the Fourier’s series for finite media and compared with Error Functions series. The value for diffusion coefficient was $D_{Mn} = 2.71 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Example of the numerical method using a computer program is reported in the Appendix.

5. Conclusions

The diffusion coefficient for manganese has been confirmed throughout a numerical method using two different routines called Fourier's and error function series. The results obtained from Fourier's and error function series demonstrates similar values among them. Secondary Ion Mass Spectroscopy Data is required to get the concentration profile against the depth of silicon. The data transformed into dimensionless parameters is useful to determine the diffusion coefficient for the transport of manganese into silicon at high temperature. The method provided in this job evaluating the diffusion coefficient as a parameter can be used to compare our results with those provided by other authors all of them looking for consistence in the numerical quantities. Diffusing manganese in silicon is purely physical and at high temperature is controlled by the concentration difference. After the diffusion it is demonstrated that the structure of the silicon remained unaltered as characterized by the Raman Spectroscopy evaluated on the surface of the substrate. The electrical property of silicon was modified by the presence of manganese as evaluated at room temperature before and after diffusing manganese. The conductivity on the surface increases when current is applied from 0.0 to 15 mA; increasing the current density lowers the conductivity as compared with silicon without manganese.

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6. References

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Appendix

Routine of a computer program to estimate the diffusion coefficient using Fourier's Series:

Fouri:=

	0	1
0	3.385·10 ⁻⁸	1.003
1	5.225·10 ⁻³	...

Length (Fouri⁽⁰⁾)=132 xL:=Fouri⁽⁰⁾

$$CCom(xlm,D) := \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^5 \frac{1}{n} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{3}\right) \cos(n\pi \cdot xlm) \cdot e^{-\left[\frac{(n\pi)^2}{2}\right] \cdot D}$$

$$Pta(xlm,D) := \left(\frac{CCom(xlm,D)}{\frac{d}{dD} CCom(xlm,D)} \right)$$

guess2 := 0.10

C2 := genfit(xL,CCo,guess2,Pta) C2:= 0.015

D:= C2 DtL:= \sqrt{D} = 0.121 DtL=2(Dif·t)^{1/2}/L1

t:= 1.5 (3600 sec) L1:= 20·10⁻⁶m

Dif:=(DtL·L1)² / t Dif= 2.711x10⁻¹⁶ m²/s

Fourier Model:

$$Fourie(x) := \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^5 \frac{1}{n} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{3}\right) \cos(n\pi \cdot xlm) \cdot e^{-\left[\frac{(n\pi)^2}{2}\right] \cdot D}$$

Routine of a computer program to estimate the diffusion coefficient using Error Function Series:

Errf :=

	0	1
0	3.385·10 ⁻⁸	1.003
1	5.225·10 ⁻³	...

Length (Errf⁽⁰⁾)=132 xL:= Errf⁽⁰⁾ CCo:= Errf⁽¹⁾

$$CCoErrf(x,DtLerr) := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=0}^4 \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x-2 \cdot n + \frac{1}{3}}{DtLerr}\right) \right) - \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x-2 \cdot n - \frac{1}{3}}{DtLerr}\right) \right)$$

$$f(x,DtLerr) := \left(\frac{CCo(xlm,D)}{\frac{d}{dD} CCom(xlm,D)} \right)$$

gerr:= 0.10

cgErr := genfit(xL,CCo,gerr,f) cgErr= 0.122

DtLerr:= 0.122 terr:= 1.5 (3600 sec) Lerr:= 20·10⁻⁶ m

Derr:=0.000000001 m²/s 0.122= 2(Derr·terr)^{1/2} / Lerr

Derr:=Find(Derr) DtL1:=0.122 Derr=2.756x10⁻¹⁶ m²/s

Error Function Model:

$$Errfm(x) := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=0}^4 \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x-2 \cdot n + \frac{1}{3}}{DtL1}\right) \right) - \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x-2 \cdot n - \frac{1}{3}}{DtL1}\right) \right)$$

